

Studies on the Synthesis and Biological Activity of some 4-(5-Aryl-2-furfurylidene)-1,3-disubstituted-2-pyrazolin-5-ones

BALAKRISHNA KALLURAYA*, JANCY K. JOHN and B. SHIVARAMA HOLLA

Department of Studies in Chemistry, Mangalore University, Mangalagangothri-574 199

Manuscript received 1 October 1992, revised 3 April 1993, accepted 9 November 1993

A series of *N*-substituted-3-methyl-4-(5-aryl-2-furfurylidene)-2-pyrazolin-5-ones (2-4) have been synthesised by the reaction of *N*-substituted-3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-5-ones with 5-aryl-2-furfuraldehyde. The compounds were evaluated for their antibacterial activity against both Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria.

Nitrofurans possess broad spectrum antibacterial properties and find application as commercial drugs¹. Attempts have been made to modify the structures of the nitrofurans by introducing carrier molecules during drug design², with a view to reducing the toxicity. One such attempt is to introduce 5-arylfuran moiety in place of 5-nitrofurans.

Substituted 5-pyrazolones possess various biological activities³. Prompted by these observations⁴ and in an attempt to minimise the toxicity, we have synthesised a series of *N*-substituted-3-methyl-4-(5-aryl-2-furfurylidene)-2-pyrazolin-5-ones (2-4) and the same is reported here.

Various 3-methyl-5-pyrazolones (1) suitably substituted at position-1 by aryl, aroyl and aryloxyacetyl groups were prepared by refluxing the respective hydrazides with ethyl acetoacetate. In order to study the structure-activity relationship, three arylfurfurals were employed for the condensation. The pyrazolones (1) were then condensed with the arylfurfurals in acetic acid medium employing sodium acetate as the catalyst to afford the title compounds (2-4) (Scheme 1). All the compounds were characterised by analytical and spectral data (Table 1).

The synthesised arylfurfurylidene pyrazolones showed halochromism with concentrated sulphuric

Scheme 1. Reagents : (i) C₂H₅OH Δ and (ii) AcOH + NaOAc, Δ.

acid, characteristic of α,β-unsaturated carbonyl compounds, thereby confirming the presence of propenone structure. Ir spectra of the pyrazolones (1) showed a strong absorption band at 1740–1760 cm⁻¹ characteristic of the ring carbonyl stretching frequency. However the ir spectra of condensed products (2-4) showed the carbonyl absorption at 1680–1720 cm⁻¹ indicating the presence of α,β-unsaturated carbonyl function. The

TABLE 1—DATA OF COMPOUNDS 2–4*

Compd. no.	R	R ¹	Yield (%) M.p. * (°C)	Colour and crystal form	Halochromism with conc. H ₂ SO ₄
2a	Phenyl	2,4-Dichlorophenyl	82 215 ^a	Brown micro-needle	Dark red
b	2,4-Dinitrophenyl	2,4-Dichlorophenyl	80 245–6 ^a	Red crystal	Dark red
c	2-Methylbenzoyl	2,4-Dichlorophenyl	72 168 ^a	Pale yellow crystal	Blood red
d	3-Nitrobenzoyl	2,4-Dichlorophenyl	45 165–66 ^a	Yellow crystal	Orange brown
e	4-Nitrobenzoyl	2,4-Dichlorophenyl	68 230 ^a	Yellow micro-crystal	Yellow
f	4-Chlorobenzoyl	2,4-Dichlorophenyl	40 235 ^a	Yellow crystal	Yellow
g	2-Hydroxybenzoyl	2,4-Dichlorophenyl	57 215–16 ^b	Yellow crystal	Orange red
h	2-Methylphenoxy acetyl	2,4-Dichlorophenyl	68 140–42 ^a	Brown crystal	Orange red
3a	Phenyl	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	80 250–52 ^a	Brown crystal	Dark red
b	2,4-Dinitrophenyl	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	82 250 ^a	Reddish brown	Red
c	2-Methylbenzoyl	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	70 170 ^a	Brown crystal	Brown
d	3-Nitrobenzoyl	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	48 220 ^a	Yellow crystal	Brown
e	4-Nitrobenzoyl	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	66 230–2 ^a	Yellow crystal	Orange red
f	4-Chlorobenzoyl	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	43 225–6 ^a	Pale brown crystal	Dark red
g	2-Hydroxybenzoyl	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	58 250 ^a	Pale yellow crystal	Orange brown
h	2-Methylphenoxy-acetyl	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	67 170 ^a	Brown crystal	Dark red
4a	Phenyl	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	82 180–83 ^a	Brown crystal	Red
b	2,4-Dinitrophenyl	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	80 290–93 ^a	Red crystals	Dark red
c	2-Methylbenzoyl	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	75 169 ^a	Brown micro-crystal	Orange red
d	4-Nitrobenzoyl	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	65 200–02 ^a	Yellow crystal	Orange yellow
e	4-Chlorobenzoyl	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	43 245–46 ^a	Yellow crystal	Orange red
f	2-Hydroxybenzoyl	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	60 240 ^a	Yellow crystal	Orange red
g	2-Methylphenoxy-acetyl	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	65 170–71 ^a	Pale brown crystal	Blood red

*All compounds gave satisfactory N analysis. **Solvent of crystallisation : ^adimethyl formamide; ^bdioxane.

arylfurfurylidene pyrazolones carrying aroyl and aryloxyacetyl substituent at position-1 also showed another band for the amide carbonyl group at 1650–1680 cm^{-1} . Similarly the nmr spectra of compounds **2f**, **2g** and **3e** are also consistent with the assigned structure. The mass spectrum of the pyrazolone (**2f**) showed intense molecular ion peak at m/z 458 and the isotope peaks at m/z 460 and 462 respectively, which is consistent with the molecular formula $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{13}\text{Cl}_3\text{N}_2\text{O}_3$.

Some selected compounds were screened in vitro against *Bacillus subtilis*, *Salmonella typhi*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Escherichia coli* at 10 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ concentration by disk-diffusion method⁵ using nitrofurazone as standard. Among the compounds tested only **2g**, **3g** and **4f** were active against certain bacteria.

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. Ir spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 237B spectrophotometer, nmr spectra (DMSO-d_6) on a Perkin-Elmer R-32 (90 MHz) spectrometer using TMS as an internal standard and mass spectra on a Jeol JMS-D-300 spectrometer operating at 70 eV. The *N*-substituted-3-methylpyrazolin-5-ones (**1**) and arylfurfuraldehydes were prepared according to the reported methods and characterised^{5,6}.

*N*₁-Substituted-3-methyl-4-(5-aryl-2-furfurylidene)-2-pyrazolin-5-one (**2-4**) : To *N*₁-substituted-3-methylpyrazolin-5-one (0.01 mol) dissolved in glacial acetic acid (20 ml), were added anhydrous sodium acetate (2.0 g) and 5-aryl-2-furfural (0.01 mol) and the reaction mixture was refluxed for

6 h. It was then cooled and poured in cold water. The solid separated was crystallised from suitable solvents : **2f** δ 2.3 (3H, s, CH_3), 6.52 (1H, s, olefinic 1H), 6.8 (1H, d, furyl 3-H), 7.1 (1H, d, furyl 4-H), 7.2–7.8 (7H, m, ArH); **2g** δ 2.5 (3H, s, CH_3), 6.93 (1H, s, olefinic H), 6.98 (1H, d, furyl 3-H), 7.13 (1H, d, furyl 4-H), 7.3–7.9 (7H, m, ArH), 11.89 (1H, s, intramolecularly hydrogen-bonded OH); **3e** δ 2.39 (3H, s, CH_3), 6.96 (1H, s, olefinic H), 7.1 (1H, d, furyl 3-H), 7.9 (1H, d, furyl 4-H), 7.5–8.1 (8H, m, ArH).

Acknowledgement

The authors thank R.S.I.C., C.D.R.I., Lucknow, and S.I.F., I.I.Sc., Bangalore, for the analytical and spectral data.

References

1. M. C. DODD and W. B. STILLMAN, *J. Pharmacol. Exp. Therap.*, 1944, **82**, 11: "The Merck Index". ed. M. WINDHOLZ, 9th. ed., Merck and Co Inc., Rahway, 1976, pp. 553, 848.
2. T. NOVINSON, B. BOOSHAN, T. OKABE, G. R. REVANKAR, R. K. ROBINS, K. SENGU and H. R. WILSON, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1976, **19**, 512; G. Y. LESHNER, US Pat. 3 516 994/1970 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1970, **73**, 56083); C. E. BERKOFF, P. N. CRAIG, B. P. GORDON and C. PELLERANO, *Arztem Forsch.*, 1970, **23**, 830 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1973, **79**, 78658).
3. R. B. PATHAK and S. C. BAIHEL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1980, **57**, 1108; V. WRZECINONO, K. PIETKICWICZ, B. KRZYSZTOFIK, W. MICHALASKA and M. DROZDOWSKIE, *Pharmazie*, 1978, **33**, 266 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1978, **80**, 129446).
4. B. S. HOLLA and B. KALLURAYA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1988, **27**, 683.
5. B. KALLURAYA, Ph.D. Thesis, Mangalore University, 1987.
6. H. AKASHI and R. ODA, *J. Chem. Soc. Jpn., Ind. Chem. Sect.*, 1952, **55**, 271 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1954, **48**, 3953; 1951, **45**, 7519).

